

Half-day seminar on Computational Creativity

Registrations are closed

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ICTEAM hosts a Francqui chair holder, Prof. Hannu Toivonen, from the University of Helsinki, Finland. Prof. Toivonen is a world-renowned expert in data mining and computational creativity. On this occasion, we are delighted to organize a half-day seminar on computational creativity.

We will explore how AI can generate, enhance, or collaborate in creative processes, producing novel outputs in various domains such as music, synthesis comic and games.

Professor Siegfried Nijssen has the pleasure to welcome the following experts:

- 13:05 : Hannu Toivonen, Professor of Computer Science at the Department of Computer Science of the University of Helsinki, Finland. He will talk about Creativity and AI
- 13:55: Peter Van Roy, Professor of Computing Science and Engineering, ICTEAM, EPL, UCLouvain. He will talk about Music composition aided by symbolic AI
- 14:20 : break
- 14:40 : Ilan Manouach, Postdoctoral researcher at ULiège, Publisher & Artist. He will talk about Haunted Comics: The indeterminate craft of prompting.
- 15:05 : Eric Piette, Professor of Computing Science and Engineering, ICTEAM, EPL, UCLouvain. He will talk about Generating Games Via Evolution and Language Models

Liens rapides

Pour plus de renseignements sur un événement, l'adresse e-mail des organisateurs est indiquée sur chaque page

d'inscription.

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